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**THE DETERMINANTS OF RETURN ON ASSETS: EVIDENCES FROM MICRO
FINANCE INSTITUTIONS IN SRI LANKA**

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Abstract

This study was undertaken with the objective of asserting the significant determinants of return on assets in Sri Lankan microfinance institutions. This study is based on eleven microfinance institutions in Sri Lanka, within the period of 2005-2010, which are practicing microfinance at present. In this study profitability is measured by return on assets ratio. Efficiency and productivity are measured by operating expense ratio, personal productivity ratio and cost per borrower ratio. Financing structure is measured by debt/equity ratio. Portfolio quality is measured by write-off ratio. The researcher postulated that, Operating Expense Ratio, Cost per Borrower Ratio and Debt/Equity Ratio are statistically significant predictor variables in determining Return on Assets Ratio. Moreover Write off Ratio is also another important predictor variable in determining Return on Assets regardless of the significance.

Key words: Efficiency, Financing structure, Microfinance, Productivity, Profitability, Return on Assets.

Introduction

Sri Lanka is well known for its noteworthy perfections in human development indicators. Though it is the fact, Sri Lanka remains a low income country (Kelegama, 2001).

The poor entail financial services particularly savings services and credit as much as the rich, or even more so (Alwis, 2008). Though there's a prerequisite of finance for the poor, inability to access formal finance has become a critical concern in this regard (Safiuddin, 2011). Besides, there is a perception that, formal financial institutions often do not meet financial needs of the poor (Alwis, 2008). Under this phenomenon, the poor often tend to resort to alternative savings methodologies such as accumulating excess funds at home and/ or saving in kind (e.g. accumulated gold, livestock and consumer durables) (Alwis, 2008). Obviously, borrowings from the informal sector are comparatively riskier. Though the informal sector gives awful repercussions, still 18.3% of households are borrowing from the informal sector (GTZ ProMis, 2009).

Starting with the Grameen Bank founded by professor Mohammad Yunus in the 1970s, microfinance is considered as a viable tool to alleviate poverty while serving to the poorest people on the globe (Ugur, 2006). In Sri Lanka microfinance is fueled by many institutions' interests, such as Regional Development Banks (RDBs) and other Licensed Specialized Banks, Co-operative Rural Banks and other co-operatives, Thrift and Credit Co-operative Societies (TCCSs), Samurdhi Bank Societies (SBSs), NGO (Non Governmental Organizations)-MFIs (Microfinance Institutions), and other financial institutions (This category includes commercial banks, registered financial companies, etc).¹

The Return on Assets Ratio (RoAR) measures how well the institution uses all its assets. Or in other words, it measures how profitable a company is relative to its total assets. RoAR gives an idea as to how efficient management is at using its assets to generate earnings (Damian von Stauffenberg et al, 2003).

Based on the regulatory and accountability phenomenon, the researcher is keen on establishing an intuitive argument, which is, microfinance sector in Sri Lanka will be more productive, if MFIs operate in a lucrative manner by means of alleviating poverty in Sri Lanka. If so, MFIs must be well designed towards profitability and towards accomplishing a moral obligation towards alleviating poverty by means of implementing microfinance programs. Eventually, it can be argued that the win-win scenario will also be attained for both parties (Ugur, 2006), (McDonald, 1997).

Objective of the study

- The study attempts to determine significant determinants of return on assets in Sri Lankan microfinance institutions.

¹ Microfinance industry report, Sri Lanka, 2009, PP 14

Review of literature

Return on assets

A narrow insistence on cost recovery and the elimination of subsidies would only force MFIs to shed the poorest from their portfolios of borrowers because they are precisely the most difficult and costly to attend, Hulme et al (1996). Hulme et al (1996) findings are indirectly related with the return on assets. As return on asset ratio is calculated excluding grants or donations from the net income that is being taken into consideration.

Indicators that are employed to evaluate organizational efficiency and profitability of MFIs, such as return on assets do not show the whole picture, Monica Brand et al (2001). They kept on emphasizing the fact that sustainability is not a sufficient measure of financial performance. Meanwhile, regulators should not penalize MFIs for higher operational costs if they can demonstrate reasonable average return on assets, Stephanie Charitonenko et al (2002).

Zeynep Ugur in (2006) developed an intuitive argument based on the notion of micro banks are the best institution to engage with microfinance. Eventually, he kept on stressing that, individual based lending 'draws on traditional banking practices and involves a standard bilateral relationship between bank and customer'. This is mostly common in East Asia and Pacific. This method appears as the most vulnerable one to weak enforcement policies and information asymmetries. Only for this type of lending the authors observe a positive return on assets.

Moreover opposing scenario occurs between Monica Brand et al (2001) findings and Zeynep Ugur's (2006) findings on return on assets. Zeynep Ugur kept on stating that return on assets is a definite metric of profitability whereas, Monica Brand and Julie Gerschick emphasized the opposite of this.

Eventually, Zeynep Ugur (2006) concluded stressing micro banks which corresponds with the highest assets are exhibiting a positive outlook in terms of the growth of their revenue and their assets. Consequently their deposits have also increased continually throughout the years suggesting that they were able to serve an increasing number of clients. Statements of Zeynep Ugur (2006) suggesting that return on assets and profitability are positively correlated.

Befekadu B. Kereta, (2007) emphasized in his findings from financial sustainability angle, it finds that MFIs are operationally sustainable measured by return on asset and return on equity and the industry's profit performance is improving over time. This is once more confirming the statements of Zeynep Ugur (2006) which stated on profitability and return on assets.

Another supporting judgment for Zeynep Ugur (2006) and Befekadu B. Kereta (2007) can be stated with reference to Peter Muriu's (2011) studies. It further defines that, return on assets remains a valuable measure of MFI's profitability. Additionally, the Microfinance Financial Reporting Standards (MFRS) recommends the use of return on assets as measures of MFI profitability rather than operational self sufficiency.

Operating Expense

To reduce costs, delegation of costs can be diminished via diversification, Diamond (1984). Moreover, economic incentive schemes to staff productivity are significant to enhance

operational efficiency, Laura Elser et al (1999). The underlying theme is that a focus on efficiency will help institutions to reach more clients and attain higher levels of profitability, Monica Brand et al (2001).

Stephanie Charitonenko et al (2002) declared the commercialization of microfinance in Sri Lankan perspective. They affirmed that in addition to bringing institution's commercial and social objectives into balance, MFIs should strive for cost effective operations. The emphasis on cost efficiency is in line with their social objectives, because increase in cost efficiency allows commensurate reduction in the interest rates.

A study on determinants of financial viability, Nimal Sanderatne (2003), defined that the operational efficiency and low administration costs have an important bearing. Besides, a study on financial performances, (Michael Tucker et al), declared that, many MFIs are not considered sustainable. By stating the fact, Michael Tucker et al confirmed that the operational efficiency is inevitable to attract funds.

The relative smaller size and shorter maturity of loans drives transaction costs higher for MFIs, Nicholas P. O'Donohoe, et al (2009). Further they asserted higher costs (especially operating costs) justify higher rates. Micro lending incurs relatively higher costs than traditional lending, with higher personal and administrative expenses because of the location of clients, small transaction size, and frequent interaction with MFI staff. The costs of providing microcredit are high because of the small size of loans, the location of clients, and the high level of interaction clients have with MFI staff. Reduction in operating expense ratio is primarily driven by reductions in non-personnel expenses, Devyani Parameshwar, et al (2010).

The operating expense ratio is an indicator of institutional effectiveness, Gray M. Woller et al, Damian et al (2003). Added to this, Gray M. Woller and Mark Schreiner asserted that, an increase in the administrative expense ratio² is hypothesized to be associated with a decrease in financial self sufficiency and vice versa.

Personal Productivity

Productivity is the amount of quality services delivered by microfinance staff to their clients and it quantifies the employees' efforts to deliver a MFIs output. By increasing productivity, a MFI can lower per unit costs, improve efficiency, and ultimately enhance self sufficiency, Geetha Nagarajan (2001). In fact, staff productivity is the primary indicator to measure the productivity, Geetha Nagarajan (2001). A MFI's entire staff is a relevant unit of service production, so the best measure of productivity collectively accounts for the efforts of front and back offices. Eventually she emphasized that, the staff productivity indicator is therefore more useful when comparing between less similar MFIs.

Incentive based systems are vital to enhance staff productivity, Isabelle Barrès (2001). To enhance efficiency, increasing staff productivity through incentive systems, transportation equipment, and establishing specialized staff positions for routine administrative functions are vital, Monica Brand and Julie Gerschick (2001).

² Administrative Expense Ratio is more or less synonymous to operating expense ratio

The lack of awareness of best practices in microfinance and the need for staff training were given as the key constraint to commercialization of microfinance, Stephanie Charitonenko et al (2002). Finally they formulated that personal productivity is a definite measurement. Allowing MFIs to offer incentive-based payments to staff; to have flexible hours of operation convenient for clients; and to engage in mobile banking, permitting them to disburse funds and collect payments outside branches, can help MFIs to minimize their operational costs. Permitting incentive-based payments to staff can help MFIs reduce portfolio risk, Stephanie Charitonenko et al (2002).

One key to achieving profitability is investing more heavily in staff costs, Robert Cull et al (2006). Devyani Parameshwar et al (2010) in MBB states that, greater efficiency also results from improved staff productivity in terms of both volume and value.

Gray M. Woller et al asserted that the staff productivity³ ratio measures the total number of staff required to produce a given level of output, as measured by borrowers. Eventually they confirmed that staff productivity is not a significant determinant of self sufficiency.

Cost per Borrower

D'Espallier, et al (2010) and Hermes, et al (2011) ideas on woman borrowers and the impact it has on the profitability are same. This confirms the negative correlation between two variables.

Gray M. Woller et al identified that the cost per borrower ratio measures the value of total monetary and in kind inputs required to produce a given level of output, as measures by borrowers. He further defined that the cost per borrower is hypothesized to be inversely associated with self sufficiency.

Write offs

Devyani Parameshwar, et al (2010) in MBB states the factors contributing to the increase in loan sizes are: Graduation of clients in mature markets to higher loan sizes, increased focus of MFIs on urban clients with higher credit needs than rural clients, introduction of individual lending and increased ticket size for the first loan to new customers by some MFIs. Here the loan size has taken into consideration as loan size is an inevitable determinant of gross loan portfolio.

Debt / Equity (Leverage)

Firms with higher leverage positions tend to have a capital structure that translates into a better performance, Modigliani et al (1958). This states that high leverage and profitability are positively correlated. Nevertheless, Rhyne et al (1992) observed somewhat different approach to Modigliani et al (1958); They stated that institution which have high capital structure with equity, is tend to be more profitable. Jonathan Conning (1999) once more confirms Rhyne and Otero's (1992) study of capital structure.

The financial viability does not mean that a MFI depends on its own funds, Nimal Sandaratne (2003). Abor (2005) postulates that, short term debt ratio is positively correlated with return on equity. In fact Abor (2005) affirmed their findings pertaining to SMEs.

³ Staff Productivity ratio is synonymous to personal productivity ratio

High leverage is related to higher profit efficiency Berger et al (2006), While, Felipe Portocarrero Maisch, et al (2006) identified that, it is important for an MFI to create a capitalization plan before beginning to look for new shareholders. The creation of this capitalization plan is step one in the process of issuing debt or equity.

Zeynep Ugur (2006) portrays this new approach to microfinance by managing debt funds and attracting commercial investors to the microfinance industry. Moreover, Nicholas P. O'Donohoe, et al (2009) studied, the leverage of mature MFIs is only slightly lower than that of traditional banks.

Microfinance institutions that employ higher debt in their capital structure are more profitable, and highly leveraged microfinance institutions are more profitable, Peter Muriu, (2011). Besides, a higher debt ratio can enhance the rate of return on equity capital during good economic times, Peter Muriu, (2011). Moreover, it also appears that NGO type of microfinance institutions rely more on debt financing relative to other type of microfinance institutions, perhaps because many are not regulated to mobilize deposits.

Data collection and sampling design

The criteria for choosing the MFIs were the availability and quality of data for a time period of 6 years (2005-2010). It is an attempt to make the database of Sri Lankan MFIs as complete as possible. Therefore, the sample consists of 66 observations. The data were provided by the "Mix Market" web site which is known as the Microfinance Information Exchange (MIX)⁴.

The study pays the greater emphasis on assessing the significant determinants of return on assets in Sri Lankan microfinance institutions. The study anticipates basing on secondary data by means of annual reports of the respective MFIs. More specifically the study heavily depends on the data gathered from MIX market database.

Methodology

One multiple regression model has been employed to assess the significant determinants of microfinance profitability in Sri Lankan microfinance institutions. To measure the determinants of return on assets, five measures are used as independent variables which were extracted from Damian von Stauffenberg et al (2003) studies⁵. Namely, Operating Expense Ratio (OER), Personal Productivity Ratio (PPR), Write-off Ratio (WoR), Cost per Borrower Ratio (CpBR), and Debt/Equity Ratio (DER). Moreover, to measure the profitability, Return on Assets Ratio (RoAR) was applied as the dependent variable.

Model of the study

$$\text{RoAR} = \alpha + \beta_1 (\text{OER}) + \beta_2 (\text{PPR}) + \beta_3 (\text{WoR}) + \beta_4 (\text{CpBR}) + \beta_5 (\text{DER}) + e$$

⁴ Data from the MIX market are reliable and it has been used by many researchers who are interest in the microfinance field. Further, the MIX market review data of MFIs for coherence and consistency, and reclassify according to international financial reporting norms.

⁵ Damian, v, S., Tor, J., Naomi, K., María, C, B, B., "Performance indicators for microfinance institutions", Technical guide, 3rd edition, July 2003

Where, α , is constant, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ and β_7 are coefficients of variables, ϵ , is the residual term.

Operationalization

The following definitions of operational variables are given in the following table.

Variable	Indicator	Measurement Level	Measurement
Profitability	Return on Assets Ratio	Ratio	Net income/ Average Assets
Determinants of profitability	Operating Expense Ratio	Ratio	Operating expenses/ Average gross portfolio
	Personal Productivity Ratio	Ratio	Number of active borrowers (excluding consumer and pawn loans) / Total staff
	Write-off Ratio	Ratio	Value of loans written-off/ Average gross portfolio
	Cost per Borrower Ratio	Ratio	Operating expenses/ Average number of active borrowers(excluding consumer and pawn loans)
	Debt/Equity Ratio	Ratio	Total liabilities / Total equity

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are formulated in the present study.

Model	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Predicted Sign
	Operating Expense Ratio		Negative
Model II	Personal Productivity Ratio	Return on Assets Ratio	Positive
	Write-off Ratio		Negative
	Cost per Borrower Ratio		Negative
	Debt / Equity Ratio		Negative

Results and discussion

Correlation analysis

Multiple correlation analysis is used in situations involving two or more independent variables and their degree of association with the dependent variable (Leonard J, 2004). Using the Pearson's Product Movement Correlation with two – tailed test of significance, the correlation analysis is carried to investigate the relationship between independent and dependent variables.

The relationship between determinants of microfinance profitability and the Return on Assets Ratio (RoAR) of microfinance institutions

Independent Variables	Return on Assets Ratio Pearson's Correlation (r)	Significant Level
Operating Expense Ratio	-.617(**)	.000
Personal Productivity Ratio	.310(*)	.011
Write off Ratio	-.104	.406
Cost per Borrower Ratio	-.577(**)	.000
Debt/Equity Ratio	-.377(**)	.002

Source: Research Data

(**) Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-Tailed)

(*) Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-Tailed)

As per the Pearson's Correlation results of the above table, Operating Expense Ratio, Cost per Borrower Ratio and Debt/Equity Ratio have a strong negative significant correlation to Return on Assets Ratio. The correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (2-Tailed). This implies that, changes in those individual variables correspond with a negative contribution towards changes in Return on Assets Ratio significantly. Moreover, the correlation between Personal Productivity Ratio and Return on Assets Ratio implies a strong positive significance correlation at the 0.05 level (2-Tailed). In fact this correlation value indicates that, changes in Personal Productivity Ratio positively contribute towards changes in Return on Assets Ratio. Finally, correlation between Write off Ratio and Return on Assets Ratio is negative and also insignificant. This depicts that; changes in the predictor variable negatively contribute towards changes in the Return on Assets Ratio.

Multiple regression analysis

Moreover, this section measures the goodness of fit of the regression line by applying the Multiple Coefficient of Determination (R^2). R^2 , measures the proportion of the total variation in the dependent variable Y explained by the Xs jointly (Gujarati D.N, 2008).

Statistics of Regression between Determinants of Microfinance Profitability and the Return on Assets Ratio (RoAR)

Regression Statistics	
R Value	.718*
R Square	.516
Adjusted R Square	.475
Standard Error	3.29429
Sum of Squares (Total)	1344.726
F- Value	12.782
Sig-F	.000*

Observations	66
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Source: Research Data

*Predictors (constant) DER, WoR, OER, CpBR

R square value stands at .516 (51.6 %), implies that 51.6 percent of fitness can be observed in the sample regression line. Furthermore, it measures 51.6 percent of the total variation in the Return on Assets Ratio, is explained by independent variables (Operating Expense Ratio, Personal Productivity Ratio, Write off Ratio, Cost per Borrower Ratio and Debt/Equity Ratio) jointly.

Conclusions

The research question formulated in this study is: **“What are the significant determinants of return on assets in Sri Lankan microfinance institutions?”**

The researcher postulated that, Operating Expense Ratio, Cost per Borrower Ratio and Debt/Equity Ratio are statistically significant predictor variables in determining Return on Assets Ratio. Moreover Write off Ratio is also another important predictor variable in determining Return on Assets regardless of the significance. Besides, 51.6 percent of the total variation in the return on assets is explained by predictor variables jointly.

Conclusions of this study constitute the results of, Monica Brand et al (2001) and Zeynep Ugur’s (2006), in profitability of MFIs, whereas, this study’s results does not constitute results of Monica Brand and Julie Gerschick study on MFI profitability.

Results of Modigliani et al (1958), Berger et al (2006), study on leverage of a MFI was not supported by the findings of the researcher.

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